

FIRM SPECIFIC FACTORS AFFECTING THE PROFITABILITY OF GENERAL INSURANCE COMPANIES OF BANGLADESH: A PANEL DATA ANALYSIS

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Insurance companies play a vital role by distributing and transferring the risk in any economy. Therefore the sustainability of this industry is critical and the stability of earnings is one of the pre-conditions to survive and grow in the long run for any sector. Keeping the importance of profitability in mind, this paper investigates the firm specific factors that affect the profitability of general insurance companies of Bangladesh. To achieve the objective, quantitative approach was applied on a sample of 13 listed general insurance companies of Bangladesh for 2005 to 2014. Return on Asset (ROA) was considered as proxy for profitability; size, age, premium growth, solvency, investment ratio and loss ratio were considered as firm specific variables affecting the profitability of general insurance companies. Considering the nature of data, correlated panels corrected standard errors (PCSEs) was applied to test the research hypothesis. The findings of this paper show that size of the firms, investment ratio and loss ratio were statistically significant at 10% level. While age, size, loss ratio show negative relationship with profitability, solvency, investment ratio and premium growth show positive relationship with profitability. The results show that large firms may not always earn better return as the firms may face diseconomies of scale. On the other hand, small firms earn a good return on asset investment because they are managed more efficiently. Moreover, financially solvent firms perform better which affects the profitability positively. The study recommends that the general insurance companies of Bangladesh give due attention to these factors to improve their performance and profitability.

Key words: *General Insurance companies, Panel Data, correlated panels corrected standard errors (PCSEs)*

1. Introduction

In 1984, with the government's decision to open insurance business for the private sector, the insurance industry of Bangladesh got new momentum. Since then, a number of private insurance companies have started their business. Though the insurance industry has grown in terms of the number of companies, still a huge portion of the market, especially the rural areas, is untouched. That means, too many insurance companies have been operating in some segments of the economy, mainly in urban and semi urban areas resulting in stiff competition.

Again, in an industry where the rivalry among existing firms is too high, earning steady profit, acquiring and holding a good portion of the market share is really difficult. Therefore, it is clear that companies with sound financial management policy, proper risk management strategy will be

able to grip the market, earn substantial profit and sustain in the long run. Many factors can affect the profitability of insurance companies. Some of these factors are driven by the external environment and therefore uncontrollable whereas some are firm specific and controllable. So, it is imperative for companies to identify and analyze the firm specific factors as proper management of these can result in better productivity. It is noteworthy to remember that a huge portion of the untapped market shows significant opportunity for this industry and firms which have the ability to sustain in the long run will reap benefit out of it. Most of the related empirical studies have focused on banking sector profitability, however, few studies are available on the performance of insurance industry. Hence, insurance industry deserves special research attention. Consequently, it is expected that this article will be useful for the stakeholders, i.e. government, insurers, investors, clients and researchers etc.

The main objective of this study is to identify and compare the factors affecting the financial profitability of Bangladeshi General Insurance Companies for the period 2005-2014. The next section gives a brief overview of the insurance industry in Bangladesh. The literature review section of this paper summarizes the findings of the related studies conducted in Bangladesh and some other countries. In light of the literature review, six firm specific variables have been identified that affect the profitability of the insurance companies. The methodology section discusses the model specification and construction of research hypothesis to meet the objective of this study. In analysis and findings section, the results of descriptive statistics, correlation metrics, test of multicollinearity, test of heteroskedasticity have been discussed. Additionally, linear regression model has been explained using correlated panels corrected standard errors (PCSEs) model. This section also identifies the statistically significant variables affecting the profitability of general insurance companies and summarizes the implications of the result.

2. Insurance industry overview

Insurance is a contractual agreement where one party transfers the risk of any damage or losses to the other party whereas the latter party compensates for the losses of the former. Simply, insurance is a mechanism to distribute the risk exposure over a number of clients. While transferring risk to the economy, insurance business helps accumulate capital, make prudent investment, enhance savings of individuals and organizations and thus mobilize the economic activities. The contribution of insurance sector in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Bangladesh was 0.36% with a growth rate of 7.61% for the fiscal year 2016-17.

The history of insurance business in Bangladesh is much older with its presence since British colonial rule. After the liberation war of Bangladesh, all insurance companies were brought under the umbrella of five corporations in the public sector, but postal life and foreign life insurance companies remained out of these. However, as the cost of continuing five corporations outweighed the returns very soon, in 1973, Sadharon Bima Corporation (SBC) was incorporated to provide general insurance and Jibon Bima Corporation (JBC) was formed to provide life insurance. Still, JBC is the only state-owned life insurance company and SBC is the only state-owned non-life

insurance company. In 1984, government decided to open the insurance business for private sector as well. Followed by the decision, several private insurance companies started their operation in 1985 and thus expanding the insurance industry in the economy. At that time, as per the Act of 1984, private sector insurance companies had to obtain 100% reinsurance protection from SBC. At present, Insurance Corporation (Amendment) Act 1990 provides that fifty percent of all insurance business relating to any public property or to any risk or liability appertaining to any public property shall be placed with the SBC and the remaining fifty percent of such business may be placed with this Corporation or with any other insurers in Bangladesh.

At present, 78 insurance companies (2 state-owned companies; 45 general insurance and 31 life insurance companies in the private sector) are operating in Bangladesh. In 1988, Bangladesh Insurance Association (BIA) was formed to uphold and safeguard the interest of the member companies. Currently, 31 life and 45 general insurance companies are under the membership of BIA. If the footprint of insurance companies in the stock market of Bangladesh is noticed, it is seen that 47 insurance companies are listed in Dhaka stock exchange (DSE) and 42 are listed in Chittagong stock exchange (CSE). If the focus is given on what is happening in the insurance industry of the outside world especially in the neighboring country, India, it is observed that the number of insurance companies in India is less than that of Bangladesh even though the economy of India is significantly larger than the economy of Bangladesh. This means a large number of companies are playing in this small economy which clearly signals a high level of competition. This stiff competition is even magnified with the changes in demographic structure and business environment, challenges from global economic slowdown and so on.

For any company, maximizing shareholders' wealth is the ultimate objective definitely. On the other side, for any business concern, it is crucial that it earns profit to run its operation smoothly, maintain a stable financial position and contribute to the overall economy. Along with other indicators, profitability is one of the most important metrics through which investors measure the performance of companies. Again, earning profit also depends on the judicious deployment of accumulated capital. Given the increasing number of insurance companies in our small economy, it is really challenging for the companies to maintain a competitive edge and earn a substantial profit.

The most common products of the non-life insurance companies in Bangladesh are fire insurance, marine insurance, motor insurance, personal accident insurance, health insurance, burglary insurance etc. However, to cope up with the increasing level of competition, some insurance companies are diversifying their product basket to cater different needs of clients from different segments and thus making the insurance service more and more specialized.

3. Literature Review

Tamzid Ahmed Chowdhury, Masud Ibn Rahman, and Syeda Rownak Afza, in their article "Perceptions of the Customers Towards Insurance Companies in Bangladesh-A Study Based on the SURVQUAL Model" analyzed behavior & attitude of clients towards insurance companies in

public and private sector and suggested some measures to improve service delivery of insurance companies. They found that both local and multinational private insurance firms provide better quality service, albeit the service cost is high, and educated and affluent people tend to prefer these firms. Moreover, they showed that fewer number of branches is a drawback for the public insurance companies to attract clients. Additionally, they suggested to tie part of salary of employees with the service rendered by the latter & feedback from clients. (Chowdhury, Rahman, & Afza, 2007)

Professor Muhammad Z Mamun, in his article “Performance Evaluation of General Insurance Companies in Bangladesh: A 1991 – 2008 Analysis” analyzed the performance of 8 general insurance companies (7 private & 1 national) found that nationalized insurance companies in Bangladesh are doing better than private insurance companies in all parameters except in income earning. He considered the trend of net premium income, investment & investment income, net claims, annual profit before taxes, total assets and share price as parameters to evaluate performance. Having some regulatory advantage the nationalized insurance company had the highest company average for net premium investment, investment income, net claim and annual profit before taxes. However, for the considered period, the growth of investment of private industry was 10% whereas the same for overall industry was 8%. His study recovered that most of the sample firms had enjoyed significant growth after 2000, but there was no specific trend. (Mamun, 2010)

Chaitra K.S and Savitha.S, in their article, “Performance Evaluation of General Insurance Corporation (GIC) of India”, analyzed the importance & performance of general insurance companies in India for the period 2008-09 to 2013-14. To measure the operational efficiency, they have analyzed the income, i.e., premium and expenses i.e., Claims, commission & other operating expenses as well. They suggested that GICs should focus on reducing operating cost while increasing the premium as the latter was varying from year to year. (K. S & S, 2014)

Rehana Fowzia and Nitai Chandra Debnath in their article “Performance Analysis of Insurance Companies in Bangladesh: A Focus on Credit Rating” did a comparative performance analysis between general insurance companies and life insurance companies and found out that life insurance companies were doing well in comparison with general insurance companies. Also they emphasized that a good credit rating is crucial to gain & maintain the confidence of related stakeholders and they recommended to check out the rating result constantly & take proper actions to recover, where necessary. (Fowzia & Debnath, 2008)

Md. Azizur Rahman, Noor Nahar Begum and Md. Anisuzzaman in their article “Efficiency Comparison between Life and Non-life Takaful Operators in Bangladesh-A Non Parametric Approach” examined the efficiency of 6 Takaful companies (of which 3 are life and 3 are non-life) and found that smaller companies have higher probability of being more efficient through utilizing the inputs to get more outputs. They used commission and management as inputs and premium and net investment income as outputs. Besides, they concluded that company size has very limited influence on efficiency changes. (Rahman, Begum, & Anisuzzaman, 2014)

Dr. Amal Yassin Almajali, Sameer Ahmed Alamro and Yahya Zakarea Al-Soub in their article “Factors Affecting the Financial Performance of Jordanian Insurance Companies Listed at Amman Stock Exchange” explored the factors that mostly affect the financial performance of 25 Jordanian Insurance Companies that are listed in Amman Stock exchange during 2002-2007 and showed that leverage, liquidity, size, management competence index have positive statistical effect on the financial performance. They added that increasing the company assets will enhance the competitive power that will lead to a good financial performance. Moreover, in one side, leverage may increase the shareholder’s return along with tax advantages but in opposite to that high leverage may increase the risk of bankruptcy by making it difficult to manage new lenders(s). (Almajali , Alamro , & Al-Soub , 2012)

Mirie Mwangi and Jane Wanjugu Murigu in their article “The Determinants of Financial Performance in General Insurance Companies in Kenya” identified the factor that influence the profitability of the general insurance companies in Kenya. As per their findings, leverage, equity capital and management competency index affect the profitability positively and size and ownership structure affect it negatively. (Mwangi & Murigu, 2015)

G M Wali Ullah, Mohammaed Nasrath Faisal and Sadaqa Tuz Zuhra in their article “Factors Determining Profitability of the Insurance Industry of Bangladesh” determined the relationship of profitability with certain independent variables i.e., underwriting risk, expense ratio, solvency margin, premium growth asset growth and company size. Using the ordinary least square regression model on the 10 years data (2005-2014) of 8 selected insurance companies listed in Dhaka stock exchange, they showed that underwriting risk and size have significant inverse relationship with profitability whereas expense ration, solvency margin and growth have the significant positive relationship with the same. (Ullah, Faisal, & Zuhra, 2016)

In the article, “Determinants of Financial Performance of The Insurance Companies: A Case of Albania” Anila Çekrezi studied the data of 5 insurance companies with private capital for the period 2008-2013 and explored the factors that affect the financial performance of Albanian Insurance Companies. That study revealed that leverage and risk have negative relationship with tangibility, i.e., fixed assets to total assets and has positive relationship with the financial performance of the selected companies. Also that study recommended that insurance companies avoid high level of leverage as it may lead to bankruptcy driven by inability to make payment of debt. Additionally, insurance company should be very cautious on the risk they take. (Çekrezi, 2015)

The study “Determinants of Profitability of General Insurance Companies Performance in Poland” by Kazimierz Ortyński identified the main factors that drive the financial performance of general insurance companies in Poland. The author observed 8 largest insurers in non-life insurance sector and found that underwriting activity and net operating expense ratio affect profitability performance negatively whereas size of a firm affects the firms positively. (Ortyński, 2016)

4.1 Methodology

This study examined the empirical findings from literature and applied those models on Bangladeshi general insurance companies. A deductive approach was followed in constructing the model. Collinear relationship among the variables were hypothesized and the study followed a quantitative approach. In order to fulfill the objective of this report, multiple regression analysis has been done on panel data. The results of multiple regression was then explained to analyze the factors affecting financial performance of general insurance companies of Bangladesh. For panel data, a number of econometrics models are available. For this study, we used correlated panels corrected standard errors model which correct any inherent econometric problem automatically before conducting the regression analysis.

4.1.1 Data Sources

The data for this study were collected from secondary sources; mainly from the published annual reports from Dhaka Stock Exchange. Currently there are 47 listed insurance companies in Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE). We did not consider life insurance companies for this study. Total of 13 general insurance companies were selected based on relative market share and at least 5 years of operation. Other firms were excluded due to non-availability of annual information and less than 5 years of operation.

4.1.2 Dependent Variable and its Measurement:

The depended variable for this study is Return on Assets (ROA). ROA is a proxy for the performance or profitability of a firm. For banks and insurance companies it is considered to be an important indicator of return from employed asset. The formula for the performance measure is given as follows:

$$\text{ROA} = \text{Earning before tax (t)} / \text{Total Assets (t)}$$

4.1.3 Explanatory Variables and their Measurement:

We look for the relationship between the profitability and other firm specific factors for general insurance companies of Bangladesh. We have identified a number of variables as independent variables from literature. The independent variables include age, size, solvency, premium growth, loss ratio and investment ratio. A brief description of these variables are given below:

a) Age of company (AGE): Age is measured by the number of year a firm is in the operation of general insurance business from the date of establishment. Some literature suggest a positive relationship between these two variables. More experienced firm can manage a firm more efficiently and generate better return on investment. Reputation also plays a great role behind this.

b) Size of company (SIZE): Financial performance may improve as a firm grow big over the time. However sometimes large firms may face diseconomies of scale and so earn poor return. The size has been captured as the natural logarithm of Asset of firm.

c) *Solvency*: Solvency refers to the ability of a firm to service its fixed obligations like interest expense. Firm with higher solvency ratio has better ability to service its debt. Solvent firms have better financial health which affects the financial performance positively in general. This ratio is measured as Total Liquid asset/Total Assets.

d) *Loss ratio (LOSS)*: This variable refers to the amount of claim incurred as a percentage of Net premium. The greater the ratio, the higher the expense ratio for the firms. It is measured as: Loss ratio = Net claims incurred / Net premiums earned.

e) *Investment ratio*: Insurance companies having a higher investment to asset ratio generate more return from capital market and money market investment. This ratio is expected to have a positive relationship with firm performance. Investment Ratio= Total long Term investment/ Total Asset

f) *Premium Growth (PG)*: Premium is the price for insurance product. Premium growth is measured as $PG = (GWP (t) / GWP (t-1)) - 1$

4.2 Research Hypotheses

The study tested the following research hypotheses formulated based on prior empirical literature.

H1. Age of a company has no relation with performance of general insurance companies in Bangladesh.

H2. The size of a company has no relation with performance of general insurance companies in Bangladesh.

H3. . Investment ratio has no relation with performance of general insurance companies in Bangladesh.

H4. Loss ratio has a no impact on the performance of general insurance companies in Bangladesh

H5. Solvency ratio has no impact on the performance of general insurance companies in Bangladesh

H6. The insurance premium growth has no relation with performance of general insurance companies of Bangladesh.

Model specification:

We used a multiple regression to test the hypothesis. The following regression model was used:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AGE_{i,t} + \beta_2 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_3 LOSS_{i,t} + \beta_4 INVESTRATIO_{i,t} + \beta_5 SOLVENCY_{i,t} + \beta_6 P_GROWTH_{i,t} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where: ROA = Return on total assets; AGE = Age of the firms; SIZE = Size of firms; LOSS = Loss ratio; INVESTRATIO = Amount of investment as a percentage of total of assets; Solvency = the amount of liquid asset as a percentage of total asset; P_Growth = Premium Growth; ϵ = is the error component for firm i at time t

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots, \beta_6$ are parameters to be estimated; i = Insurance company $i = 1, \dots, 13$; and t = the index of time periods and $t = 1, \dots, 10$

5. Analysis and Findings

Descriptive statistics:

Variable	Observation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Min	Max
ROA	130	0.0912	0.054	-0.16833	0.4849
AGE	130	17.19	7.19	5	29
SIZE	130	6.87	0.98	4.8	8.9
Premium Growth	130	0.105	0.268	-0.89	1.13
Loss Ratio	130	0.22	0.1927	-0.123	1.955
Investment Ratio	130	0.4	0.26	0.021	0.9
Solvency	130	2.59	1.839	0.3544	9.27

The table shows the mean, standard deviation, maximum & minimum values for the data. From the table we see that the Return on Asset as a measure of profitability shows significant variations as it ranges from -16.83% to 48.49%. It implies that some firms incur loss while other firms could generate profit as high as 50%. The firms considered for analysis is at least 5 years old and the oldest one has an experience of 29 years. Size of the firm has been measured by taking natural logarithm of asset volume. The analysis include both small, medium & large sized firms. The firms experienced as high as 113% premium growth as indicated by the maximum value. Investment ratio had an average of 40% with a range of 2.1% to 90%. It indicates that most of the firms invest a substantial amount of fund in marketable securities, bonds or sock. It is evident because in capital market of Bangladesh, Insurance companies have significant institutional investments.

Correlation Matrix Analysis:

Variables	AGE	SIZE	PREMIUM GROWTH	LOSS RATIO	INVESTMENT RATIO	SOLVENCY
AGE	1					
SIZE	0.59	1				
PREMIUM GROWTH	0.098	0.1844	1			
LOSS RATIO	-0.0941	-0.0139	-0.1538	1		
INVESTMENT RATIO	-0.1224	-0.0043	0.68	0.0161	1	
SOLVENCY	0.59	0.4096	-0.02	-0.058	0.1296	1

From the correlation matrix, we see that Size, premium growth, solvency are positively related to age where as loss ratio and investment ratio are negatively correlated. Firm size is positively related with premium growth & solvency but negatively related with investment ratio and loss ratio. Loss ratio is inversely related to age, size and premium growth. In order to check if there is any presence of multicollinearity problem, we have observed the degree of correlation among the variables. A regression model may have multicollinearity problem if the independent variables show any high correlation among themselves. The table shows that none of the independent variables have correlation higher than 0.8. We can primarily conclude that the model does not have such problem.

Test of multicollinearity: In order to diagnose the model we applied the variable inflator factor (VIF) test. A VIF test is done to diagnose any multicollinearity problem. If the VIF value is higher than 10 or the inverse of VIF which is also known as level of tolerance is less than .10 then the model is said to have multicollinearity problem.

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
Age	2.45	0.41
Size	1.4	0.71
Investment Ratio	1.22	0.82
Premium Growth	1.09	0.92
Loss Ratio	1.09	0.92
Solvency	4.25	0.24
Mean VIF	1.92	0.67

The table shows that all of the variables have a VIF factor lower than 10. As a result the level of tolerance is also higher than 0.10. The average VIF is 1.92 which is lower than the threshold value. Therefore we can conclude that the model is free from multicollinearity problem. The primary findings in correlation matrix is now thus confirmed.

Test of Heteroskedasticity:

Due to differences in the sizes of the firms, we need to check if the model has the problem of heteroskedasticity. When the error variances are not constant then this problem arises.

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Ho: Constant variance

Variables: fitted values of ROA

chi2(1) = 1.55

Prob > chi2 = 0.2135

To diagnose the problem we used the Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test. The null hypothesis is that the model has constant variance. At 5% level of significance we fail to reject the null hypothesis of constant variances. Therefore we can conclude that the model is homoskedastic.

Linear regression, correlated panels corrected standard errors (PCSEs)

Regression Output

ROA	Coefficient	Standard Error	z	Probability
Age	-0.00055	0.00081	-0.6821	0.490
Size	-0.00885	0.00488	-1.81311	0.070**
Premium Growth	0.01030	0.0117	0.880342	0.375
Loss Ratio	-0.44000	0.230366	-1.91	0.056**
Investment Ratio	0.02978	0.012892	2.31	0.021*
Solvency	0.00277	0.002794	0.99	0.321
Constant	0.15016	0.02361	6.36008	0.000

*Statistically significant at 5% level.

** Statistically significant at 10% level. [Output generated using STATA 12.0]

Since the data set is panel in nature, we conducted multiple linear regression using correlated panels corrected standard errors (PCSEs) model. The reason for using this model is that this model automatically corrects any problem of autocorrelation or heteroskedasticity in panel data set. The overall multiple regression is statistically significant at 5% level.

Age: Age shows a negative relationship with performance of Bangladeshi Insurance companies. It implies that firm with more years of experience not necessarily shows better financial performance. However we find age statistically insignificant at 5% level.

Size: Firm size is negatively related with financial profitability. It indicates that firms with larger asset base may not be able to generate greater profit as they might face diseconomies of scale suggested by many authors. This variable is statistically significant at 10% level. 1% increase in size of firm results in 0.88% decrease in ROA for Bangladeshi insurance firms. This finding is consistent with the findings of Mwangi & Murigu (2015).

Premium growth rate: Premium growth rate has a positive relation with ROA. However this positive relationship is not statistically significant at 5% level. Higher premium growth rate indicates a persistent rise in price of insurance product. The relationship suggest that an increase in premium increases the revenue and profit of insurance companies of Bangladesh.

Loss ratio: Loss ratio is expressed as claim incurred as a percentage of premium earned. As the claims of insurance fall due the insurance companies incur liability which reduces the profitability of firm. The relationship therefore is negative with ROA and empirical finding is consistent with the hypothesis. This variable is found statistically significant at 5% level of significance.

Investment Ratio: Insurance companies, particularly general insurance companies are the largest institutional investors in capital markets of Bangladesh. The investment income in the form of interest income, dividends are major earning sources for these firms. As expected the relationship between investment ratio and ROA is positive for Bangladeshi firms. This relationship is statistically significant at 5% level of significance.

Solvency Ratio: Solvent firms are more likely to generate better return on asset as compared to insolvent firms. Although the relationship between solvency and ROA is positive, this variable is not statistically significant at 5% level. The favorable impact of solvency margin on profitability of Bangladeshi general insurance firms are confirmed by the findings of Ullah, Faisal, & Zuhra (2016)

The summary of empirical findings are listed below:

Variable	Theoretically Expected Relationship with ROA	Empirically found relationship with ROA	Hypothesis Test Results at 10% level of significance
Age	+	-	H1 Accepted
Size	+/-	-	H2 Rejected
Loss Ratio	-	-	H3 Rejected
Investment Ratio	+	+	H4 Rejected
Solvency	+	+	H5 Accepted
Premium Growth	-	+	H6 Accepted

6. Conclusion

This paper investigates the factors that affect the financial performance of general insurance companies of Bangladesh. With a total of 78 insurance companies currently operating in Bangladesh, the insurance industry is extremely competitive. In a small economy like Bangladesh, the intense competition actually drives the average industry profitability down. In this context, the assessment of factors responsible for financial profitability of these firm is a major concern. Most of the previous studies on insurance companies of Bangladesh focused on the analysis of financial performance only; not on the factors affecting the financial performance. This paper provides some empirical insight on the financial profitability of General insurance companies of Bangladesh. The study shows that firms with large asset base do not always perform better. It may imply the diseconomies of scale that lead to inefficiencies and poor financial performance for these firms. Moreover, age and loss ratio also negatively affect the financial performance. On the other side

firms with a substantial investment in stock, bonds generate greater return as compared to their peers. The solvent firms with good standing in terms of debt servicing capabilities earn greater profit. The high growth in premium also improves financial performance. The scope of this study was limited to firm specific factors of non-life general firms only. Further study can be done in future by taking the macroeconomic variables into account to assess the financial performance of both life and no life firms. We hope that government, companies, investors and policymakers will find the findings of this study useful. While firms can consider these factors carefully and enhance their profitability, investors can use these factors as screening mechanisms to identify which firm to invest in. Regulators can closely monitor these factors and assess the chances of bankruptcy by these insurance companies. In a nutshell, this study can serve as a corner stone for further research in this sector.

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